

Prostate cancer championship phase V4

ID: a092a929-ef5b-41f2-93ee-9231c56beeb6

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/a092a929-ef5b-41f2-93ee-9231c56beeb6/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 736

Subjects count: 732

Age range: Between 46 years and 86 years

Sex: Male, Unkown

Body part(s): PROSTATE, ARM, PELVIS, Pelvis^Masculin, ABDOMEN, HEAD, PANCREAS, CHESTABDPELVIS, Unknown

Modality: MR